

Comparative Analysis of Funding of Students' Personnel Services in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

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Abstract

This study compared funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. It adopted descriptive research design of survey type. The population for the study comprised all the 2,325 (female 1,327; male, 998) teachers in the 42 public secondary schools and 2,229 (female 1,219; male, 1,010) teachers in the 48 private secondary schools in the local government area in 2022/2023 academic session. Random sampling technique was used to select 21 public and 24 private secondary schools, while 10 teachers were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools to make a sample of 450. Questionnaire entitled "Funding of Students' Personnel Services Questionnaire" was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire was validated, tested for reliability and found reliability coefficient of .81. Inferential statistic of t-test was used to test the hypotheses formulated. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government ($p < .05$). The study concluded that funding of students' personnel services was performed better in private secondary schools than public in Ilorin West Local Government. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among other things that government should intensify its efforts in funding students' personnel services like proprietors of private schools, while the proprietors of private schools should not relent in giving personnel services a priority, in order to continually provide a supportive and conducive environment for students to learn and consequently boost their academic performance.

Keywords: Funding, Students' Personnel Services; Library Service, Guidance and Counselling Services, Co-curricular Services

Introduction

Funding is an important instrument for achieving the goals of education, regardless of the level. It is a very key necessity which significant determines school success (Salman, 2022). Funding could be adjudged as one of the factors which is responsible for variation in the effectiveness of schools in Nigeria (Adekola, 2022). A school that is well-funded is likely to operate better than the one that is funded poorly. However, one of the areas where school proprietors need to ensure adequate funding on, in order to achieve the goal(s) for which the schools are established is students' personnel services such as library services, information communication services, health services, guidance and counselling services, co-curricular services and

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the likes (Yusuf, et al, 2019). According to Odediji, et al. (2023), funding is the process of making money available for effective running of a private or public organization in order to actualize the stated goals. Elujekwute, et al. (2021) stated that funding refers to provision of financial resource for the success of an organization. Ogungbenle and Edogiawerle (2019) explained that funding is a crucial resource which schools need to achieve the stated goals. Adequate provision of funds is a strong base upon which the smooth operation of every aspect of any educational enterprise is built. Ahmed and Oweh (2013) submitted that inadequate funding is one of the problems facing educational system in Nigeria, irrespective of the level. Adewuyi and Okemakinde (2013) opined that considering the role which education plays in the socio-economic development of Nigeria, it is very crucial that both government and private investors in education ensure adequate provision of financial resource for schools. Nwafor, et al. (2015) maintained that all the stakeholders in education believe that the quality of funding made available to a school is a great determinant of the quality of its outputs. Odediji, et al. (2023) maintained that no secondary school can effectively operate without adequate funding. Apart from adequate provision of student personnel services, funding is required for the payment of workers' salaries, provision for and maintain infrastructural facilities and to keep the school at proper condition Adequate provision of funds for schools is very sacrosanct to the smooth to the actualization of schools' goals. However, one of the areas which adequate funding is needed for schools to achieve the stated goals is in the area of students' personnel services. According to Abdullahi (2017), students' personnel services can be defined as all activities carried out by managers, teachers and non-teaching staff in order to make school conducive for learning for students, make them happy, useful and become better citizens of the society in which they belong. Yusuf, et al. (2019) elucidated students' personnel services as various services which are provided for students by school management, with the purpose of helping them to succeed in their academic activities. This is necessary not only to ensure that students gladly learn but also ensure that the stated goals achieved. Ebirim, et al. (2014) maintained that students' personnel services are an important aspect of school system and they constitute the needs which would assist students to achieve their educational dreams. No educational system, irrespective of the level, cannot effectively operate without these services and their provision greatly support the success of the schools.

Usman (2015) asserted that the poor performance of students in secondary schools in Nigeria could be due inadequate provision of personnel services to students. Bradley et al. (2015) stated that adequate provision of students' personnel services makes students comfortable, and this helps in greatly contributing to not only the peace of mind but also effective learning of students. The aspects of students' personnel services which this study covered were library, guidance and counselling and co-curricular services. Onuoha and Chukwueke (2020) viewed a library as a systematized assemblage of sources of information resources made available for students for reference or borrowing, in order to boost their academic performance. In addition, school library serves as the channel for ensuring availability of physical or digital access to materials which help support students' effective learning. Agbo (2015) maintained that library services are very important because of its role in improving the academic development of students. Through library services, students have access to a pool of textbooks, newspapers, periodicals, magazines, journals, computers, films, recordings or videotapes which help to enrich their knowledge in their various subjects of learning and other aspects of learning. Nkamnebe, et al. (2017) noted that library services in general term cover reference services, lending services, referral services, document delivery, electronic mail services, current awareness services, selective dissemination of information, reprographic services, indexing and abstracting services, bibliographic services and online searching amongst others. If all these are adequately provided and students make effective use of them, it would help enhance their academic success. The findings of the study conducted by Verma (2015) revealed that school library plays an important role in the academic success of students. No educational institution is complete without effective library services provision for students. In addition, the findings of Strong (2013) showed that there was a significant relationship between library services and students' academic attainment and sustainable education in the United States of America.

Another aspect of students' personnel services which is highly needed to be given adequate attention in schools is guidance and counselling. Abdullahi (2017) stated that guidance and counselling services are a crucial aspect of students' personnel services. This is because it is a channel that is based on desirable advisory techniques, aimed at helping students to actualise their aspirations and goals. Through guidance and counselling, emotional problems, frustration or upheavals which are troubling the students' minds are removed. To buttress the importance of guidance and counselling services to students, the findings of the study conducted by Anagbogu, et al. (2013) revealed that there was a significant relationship between guidance and counseling services and academic success of students. Owan and Ekaette (2019) opined that guidance and counseling services are a significant aspect of students' personnel services. This educative act aims at helping students to develop competencies and skills that could assist them to make decisions that would make them live impactful lives and at the same time aptly make their contributions to the national development. Etebu, et al. (2016) submitted that guidance and counseling is an important component of educational system and so, it is very imperative that every school is provided with trained counselors

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saddled with the responsibility of dishing out professional guidance and counseling services to students, to make them solve any problem which could hinder their effective learning. Ali and Ogundele (2015) believed that it is very crucial for schools to have effective guidance and counselling services so as to provide the necessary support for students in the choice of career. Ogundele, et al. (2018) concluded that provision of real guidance and counseling services needs to be given an utmost consideration. The quality level of guidance and counseling services provided for secondary school students would enable them to fathom their potentials and able to take right decisions which would aid their academic success. Another aspect of students' personnel services which needs adequate funding is co-curricular services. Othoo and Omondi (2022) explained co-curricular activities as those activities sponsored or recognised by a school which are not part of the academic curriculum but are approved to be an indispensable part of school system. Co-curricular activities consist of sports, clubs or associations which are performed based on students' willingness. They are activities carried out outside the realm of students' academic activities. Bryant, et al. (2015) believed that co-curricular services are an essential aspect of students' personnel services. Through effective co-curricular services, students' overall development is enhanced. Hence, there is need for school managers to ensure the services are operated smoothly in schools. Chang and Shon (2015) asserted that the importance of co-curricular services in educational system cannot be over-emphasised. This is because the services help to meet the needs and aspirations of the students; foster unity among students; make students to be fit physically; changes the school tone; and prepares students for future tasks. To support the above claims, the findings of the study conducted by (2013) revealed that there was a significant relationship students' personnel services (co-curricular services) and academic performance of students.

Students' personnel services in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government needs to be given adequate attention in order to boost students' academic performance. However, despite the great contributions of students' personnel services to the academic success of students, seems not getting the due attention in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, especially in the aspects of library, co-curricular and guidance and counselling services (Sunday, 2021). For instance, some schools in this area do not have a building that could be regarded as the school library while the existing ones in other schools are seriously suffering from lack of professional librarian and lack or insufficiency of current adequate textbooks, magazines, newspapers, journals, internet facilities and other resources for students' self-study or research which help to enhance their academic performance. Not only that, some of these schools do not have sporting and other resources which could aid effective conduct of co-curricular services, in spite of its role in boosting physical and mental development of students (Adekunle, 2020). In addition, guidance and counselling services as integral as it is to education has gone to the state of redundancy in some of these schools, because of absence of well-equipped counselling unit (Adekola, 2021). All these challenges are majorly bothered on inadequacy of funds to these schools.

Some researchers had conducted studies related to this present study. For instance, Chidobi (2015) investigated management of student personnel services in public secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone for sustainability of quality human resources for national development. The findings of the study revealed that management of student personnel services in public secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone for sustainability of quality human resources for national development was average. Paul (2015) carried out student personnel management: A panacea for effective secondary school administration in Nigeria. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between student personnel management and effective secondary school administration in Nigeria. Akpan and Onabe (2016) investigated management of students' personnel services and sustainable secondary education in Calabar education zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that there was significant relationship between management of students' personnel services and sustainable secondary education in Calabar education zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. However, none of these previous studies compared the scenario of students' personnel services in both private and public secondary schools. Hence, this study was set out to compare funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, in order to determine the kind of attention given to this important aspect of education in the two school types. Determining the attention given to students' personnel services in the two school types would help to determine which school type performs better in that aspect, so that necessary improvement could be made where necessary, in order to boost students' performance academically. This is the gap which this study filled.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to compare the:

1. funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government;
2. funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government;

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3. funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government; and
4. funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised.

1. Is there significant difference between funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government?
2. Is there significant difference between funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government?
3. Is there significant difference between funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government?
4. Is there significant difference between funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated.

1. There is no significant difference between funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.
2. There is no significant difference between funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.
3. There is no significant difference between funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.
4. There is no significant difference between funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Methodology

This study compared funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. It adopted descriptive research design of survey type. The population for the study comprised all the 2,325 (female 1,327; male, 998) teachers in the 42 public and 2,229 (female 1,219; male, 1,010) in 48 private secondary schools in the Local Government Area. Random sampling technique was used to select 21 public and 24 private secondary schools, while 10 teachers were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools to make a total of 450 respondents. "Funding of Students' Personnel Services Questionnaire" was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire was divided into the three sections (A: Library Services; B: Guidance and Counselling Services & C: Curricular Services). The researcher and two research assistants administered questionnaire to the respondents. The questionnaire was validated by three experts in the field of Educational Management, tested for reliability and found reliability coefficient of .81 was obtained. Inferential statistic of t-test was used to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. Four hundred and twenty-two (public, 194; & 228, private) copies of the questionnaire retrieved were used for analysis. t-test was used to test all the hypotheses. Out of the 210 copies of the questionnaire distributed to respondents in public secondary schools and 240 copies distributed to respondents in private schools, only 194 and 228 copies were retrieved from public and private schools respectively.

Results

Research hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

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Table 1: t-test Showing Significant Difference in the Funding of Students' Personnel Services in public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

School type	<u>X</u>	SD	p-va	p-value	Decision
Public	3.48	1.09		0.004	Ho ₁ Rejected
Private	4.41	0.83			

Field Report (2023)

Table 1 shows the p-value (0.004) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference in the funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Table 2: t-test Showing Significant Difference between the Funding of Library Services in public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

School type	<u>X</u>	SD	p-va	p-value	D Decision
Public	3.64	0.95		0.001	Ho ₂ Rejected
Private	4.16	1.27			

Field Report (2023)

Table 2 shows the p-value (0.001) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Research hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Table 3: t-test Showing Significant Difference between the Funding of Guidance and Counselling Services in public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

School type	<u>X</u>	SD	p-p	p-value	Eci Decision
Public	3.30	1.11		0.027	Ho ₃ rejected
Private	4.64	1.53			

Field Report (2023)

Table 3 shows the p-value (0.027) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Research hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between the funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

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Table 4: t-test Showing Significant Difference between the Funding of Co-curricular Services in public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

School type	\bar{X}	SD	p-value	Decision
Public	3.51	1.20	0.011	Ho ₄ Rejected
Private	4.43	1.39		

Field Report (2023)

Table 4 shows the p-value (0.011) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the funding of curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference between the funding of curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. The mean score of private schools (4.41) which is greater than that of the public schools (3.48) shows that funding of students' personnel services was better in private than public secondary schools. This finding agrees with the finding of Garuba (2017) that the provision of students' personnel services was better in private than public secondary schools in Ofu Local Government Area, Kogi State.

The findings of the study showed that there was a significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. The mean score of private schools (4.16) which is greater than that of the public schools (3.64) connotes that funding of library services was better in private than public secondary schools. This supports the finding of Adaralegbe (2020) that the library services provision was better in private than public secondary schools in secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government Area, Oyo State.

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the funding of guidance and services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. The mean score of private schools (4.64) which is greater than that of the public schools (3.30) signifies that funding of guidance and counselling services was better in private than public secondary schools. This finding is in tandem with submission of Alarape (2020) that guidance and counselling services play a significant role in the life of every secondary school student but it is worrisome that attention which this aspect of students' personnel services receives in some public secondary schools in Niger State is not encouraging; as this is not comparable with the attention which the managements of some private secondary schools give to it in the state.

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. The mean score of private schools (4.43) which is greater than that of the public schools (3.51) shows that funding of students' personnel services was better in private than public secondary schools. This finding agrees with the finding of Garuba (2017) which revealed that the co-curricular services provided in private was better than public secondary schools in Ofu Local Government Area, Kogi State.

Conclusion

The study concluded that funding of students' personnel services was performed better in private secondary schools than public in Ilorin West Local Government; funding of library services in private secondary schools was given better attention than public in Ilorin West Local Government; funding of guidance and counselling services was done better in private secondary schools than public in Ilorin West Local Government; and funding of co-curricular services was given a better attention in private secondary schools than public in Ilorin West Local Government.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. government should intensify its efforts in funding students' personnel services like proprietors of private schools, while the proprietors of private schools should not relent in giving personnel services a priority, in order to continually provide a supportive and conducive environment for students to learn and consequently boost their academic performance;

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2. government should ensure that well-equipped library is provided for schools which do not have while the existing ones which are in the state of moribund should be renovated and well-equipped while the managements of private secondary schools should continue to give funding of library services proper attention in order enhance students' academic success;
3. there is need for government to give guidance and counselling services a more befitting attention, while the proprietors of private secondary schools continually strive in giving guidance and counselling its due attention, in the interest of students' academic success.
4. government should intensify more efforts in providing adequate financial support which would resuscitate effective provision of co-curricular services in public schools, while the private secondary school managements should not rest on their oars in the provision of adequate support to co-curricular services for the purpose of helping students to succeed academically.

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